

EFFECT OF PRANAYAMA ON VITAL CAPACITY AMONG COLLEGE WOMEN

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Abstract

In this context, the investigator made an attempt to investigate the effect of yogic practices on vital capacity among college women. To achieve the purpose of the study, thirty women were randomly selected as subjects from A.V.V.M. Sri Pushpam College, Poondi, Thanjavur. The age of the subjects were ranged from 18 to 21 years. The subjects selected for this study were divided into two groups of fifteen subjects each. The experimental group I underwent yoga training and group II acted as a control group. The subjects were exposed to a yoga training programme for six weeks. The training programmes were organized in a progressive manner. The obtained data from the experimental and control groups initial and final readings were statistically analyzed with analysis of covariance (ANCOVA). The level of confidence which was fixed at 0.05 levels was considered as an appropriate one for this study. It was observed that the experimental group has significantly improved the vital capacity.

Key Words: Pranayama, Vital Capacity

Introduction:

The word Pranayama derives from the Sanskrit words prana and ayama, translating as "life force" and "expansion" respectively. It is a common term for various techniques for accumulating, expanding and working with prana. In yoga, pranayama is a practise of specific and often intricate breathing techniques. Many pranayama techniques are designed to cleanse the energetic channels called nadis allowing for greater movement of prana. Other techniques may be utilized to arrest the breath for samadhi or to bring awareness to specific areas in the practitioner's subtle or physical body. It can also be utilized to generate inner heat as in the practice of tummo. In ayurveda and therapeutic yoga, pranayama may also be utilized for any number of tasks including to affect mood and aid indigestion (Balayogi et al. 2003).

Methodology:

In this context, the investigator made an attempt to investigate the effect of yogic practices on vital capacity among college women. To achieve the purpose of the study, thirty women were randomly selected as subjects from A.V.V.M. Sri Pushpam College, Poondi, Thanjavur. The age of the subjects were ranged from 18 to 21 years. The subjects selected for this study were divided into two groups of fifteen subjects each. The experimental group I underwent yoga training and group II acted as a control group. The subjects were exposed to a yoga training programme for six weeks. The training programmes were organized in a progressive manner. The obtained data from the experimental and control groups initial and final readings were statistically analyzed with analysis of covariance (ANCOVA). The level of confidence which was fixed at 0.05 levels was considered as an appropriate one for this study.

Results:

Table 1: Computation of Mean and Analysis of Covariance of Vital Capacity of Experimental and Control Groups

	Experimental Group	Control Group	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Square	F
Pre Test Mean	2.83	2.82	BG	0.001	1	0.001	0.027
			WG	0.874	28	0.031	
Post Test Mean	3.27	2.84	BG	1.404	1	1.404	40.221*
			WG	0.977	28	0.035	
Adjusted Post Mean	3.27	2.84	BG	1.342	1	1.342	124.181*
			WG	0.292	27	0.011	

* Significant at 0.05 level Table value for df 1 and 28 was 4.20, 1 and 27 was 4.21

The above table indicates the adjusted mean value of vital capacity of experimental and control groups were 3.27 and 2.84 respectively. The obtained F-ratio of 124.181 for adjusted mean was greater than the table value 4.21 for the degrees of freedom 1 and 27 required for significance at 0.05 level of confidence. The result of the study indicates that there was a significant difference among experimental and control groups on vital capacity. The above table also indicates that both pre and post test means of experimental and control groups

differ significantly. The pre, post and adjusted post mean values of vital capacity of both experimental and control groups are graphically represented in the figure 1.

Figure 1: Shows the mean values on vital capacity of experimental group and control groups

Conclusion:

It was observed that the experimental group has significantly improved the vital capacity.

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